

Education of experts for science, research and innovation

Annual monitoring: 2024

National Training Fund

Aggregations of field of study used

Humanities and social sciences

- Education (ISCED 1)
- Arts and humanities (ISCED 2)
- Social sciences, journalism and information (ISCED 3)

Natural sciences

- Natural sciences, mathematics and statistics (ISCED 5)

ICT

- Information and communication technologies (ISCED 6)

Technical fields

- Engineering, manufacturing and construction (ISCED 7)

Agricultural fields

- Agriculture, forestry, fisheries and veterinary (ISCED 8)

Health and welfare

- Health and welfare (ISCED 9)

Business, administration and law (ISCED 4) and Services (ISCED 10) are included in the category „Others“.

Structure of doctoral students and graduates – by field of study

Picture 1: Share of doctoral students by field of study

Source: MEYS: Statistics of performance indicators of public and private universities, own processing

In the Czech Republic, the number of doctoral students has been declining in recent years due to unfavorable demographic developments. From 23.9 thousand doctoral students in 2015, their number dropped to 18.3 thousand in 2024.

A significant decrease in the number of doctoral students was recorded in the humanities, social sciences and especially in technical fields. Despite the demographic decline, natural sciences and health fields enjoyed a slight increase in the number of doctoral students.

Picture 2: Share of doctoral graduates by field of study

The development of the number of doctoral graduates follows, with some delay, the development of the number of students when taking into account the success of the study. In 2024, the negative trend in the share of graduates of technical and agricultural fields was reversed.

A continuous decline is being recorded in humanities and social sciences, which produced 21% of graduates in 2024.

The share of doctoral graduates in ICT fields increased by 1 percentage point compared to previous years, but remains very low.

Despite a slight decrease in the number of graduates, natural science fields maintain their priority position in the share of doctoral graduates.

Source: MEYS: Statistics of performance indicators of public and private universities, own processing.

Full-time and combined forms of study in doctoral programs

Picture 3: Share of doctoral students enrolled in full-time studies for the first time by field of study

Source: MEYS: Statistics of performance indicators of public and private universities, own processing.

In recent years, doctoral students have increasingly preferred the full-time form of study. As of 2024, more than 80% of doctoral students in most subject groups started full-time, while in natural science and agricultural fields, the combined form at the beginning of doctoral studies is quite exceptional. A relatively high proportion of students starting the combined form persists in medicine and in the fields of business, administration and law (ISCED 4) and services (ISCED 10), but it is also decreasing here. In 2024, compared to the previous years monitored, the proportion of the combined form of study increased in the humanities and social sciences.

The growth in the share of full-time doctoral students probably reflects a certain release of university capacities as a result of demographic decline and, in this context, a greater interest of universities in recruiting full-time doctoral students, whom schools can involve more in research projects and teaching compared to distance students. The growing representation of full-time students can also be considered a manifestation of schools' efforts to improve the quality of doctoral studies.

Doctoral studies in international comparison (Czech Republic vs. EU)

The share of doctoral students among all university students in the Czech Republic is high in European comparison, in 2023 it was 6% compared to 4% in the EU. This share has not changed significantly in the Czech Republic in recent years. The Czech Republic is also one of the countries with the highest share of doctoral students in terms of population, which is also influenced by the length of study in individual countries.

The quantity of students in the Czech Republic does not lead to the desired education of experts, as a much smaller proportion of doctoral students in the Czech Republic complete their studies with graduation diploma compared to other EU countries. The ratio between graduates of doctoral programs and students of these programs (doctoral completion rate) is improving compared to the EU average, but it is still lower. The Czech Republic's gap from the EU was 5 p.p. in 2022, and 3 p.p. in 2023.

The most problematic situation is in the natural sciences, health sciences and ICT, which lag the most behind the EU level in terms of completion rates. On the contrary, agricultural fields exceed the EU average in this respect. Measures aimed at increasing the success rate of completing doctoral studies should lead to a reduction in the gap between the Czech Republic and the EU.

Picture 4: Scope and capacity of doctoral studies in the Czech Republic and the EU

*Share of doctoral students in the total number of students

Source: Eurostat (educ_uoe_grad02, educ_uoe_enrt02), own processing.

Doctoral studies in international comparison (Czech Republic vs. EU)

Picture 5: Scope and rate of completion of doctoral studies – international comparison

Compared to individual EU countries, the Czech Republic was in second place after Germany in terms of the scope of doctoral studies in 2023. On the other hand, in terms of graduation rates, it ranks among the worst within the EU 27.

Six other EU member states reported lower graduation rates than the Czech Republic in 2023, with the closest situation in Romania and Austria.

The highest doctoral graduation rates are observed in Italy and France, behind which the Czech Republic lags by about 10 percentage points.

In countries such as Cyprus and Greece, doctoral studies have a low scope and a low graduation rate.

Source: Eurostat (educ_uae_grad02, educ_uae_enrt02) Data for 2022. Own processing.

* Share of doctoral graduates in the number of doctoral students.

** Share of doctoral students in the total number of university students.

Age at the time of completion of doctoral studies

In 2024, the average age of doctoral graduates increased by 1 year to 35.1 years compared to 2015. This development is associated with a higher risk of not completing their studies, as studies are shifted to the period when young people start families. This can have a negative impact, especially for women.

Among the oldest doctoral graduates are medical graduates, although their average age is slightly decreasing. At the same age of 36.9, doctoral students in business, administration and law (ISCED 4) and in services (ISCED 10) also graduate. With the exception of humanities and social sciences and health fields, a trend of "aging" of graduates is evident in all other fields.

The increasing age of graduates is influenced by a number of factors, including in particular the increasing age of master's degree graduates, the fact that graduates do not always enter doctoral studies immediately after completing their master's degree, or the transition of most programs from a three-year to a four-year standard period of study. However, the most important factor is the interruption and extension of the doctoral study itself.

Picture 6: Average age at doctoral graduation

Source: MEYS: Statistics of performance indicators of public and private universities, own processing.

Discontinuing doctoral studies: field of studies

Students studying in a combined form are more likely to interrupt their doctoral studies. These students face problems related to balancing the time demands placed on them by simultaneously performing their profession, studying, and often caring for dependent members of the extended family. In both years monitored, doctoral students in agricultural fields interrupted their studies most often, both in full-time and combined forms. On the contrary, students in technical fields used this option least in both forms of study.

In full-time studies, the share of interrupted studies in 2024 decreased compared to 2015, most significantly in agriculture, natural sciences and medicine. There was a slight increase only in humanities and social sciences.

Even in the combined form of study, there has been a trend towards a decrease in the rate of interruption of studies. This trend has been most pronounced in agricultural fields, ICT, and in the fields of business, administration, law, and services.

Picture 7: Share of interrupted doctoral studies in the number of full-time and part-time students

Source: MEYS: Statistics of performance indicators of public and private universities, own processing.

Discontinuing doctoral studies: men and women

Picture 8: Doctoral study dropout rate* for women and men by form of study

In the longer term, the differences between men and women in the interruption of full-time doctoral studies are deepening. While in 2010 men and women interrupted at a similar rate, in subsequent years the interruption rate for women increased, while for men it decreased. In 2024, women interrupted their studies almost three times more than men.

In the combined form of study, the differences in interruption of studies were quite significant already in 2010, and the difference deepened over time. At the beginning of the monitored period, the interruption rate for women was about 1/3 higher than for men, in 2024 it was more than double. The increasing average age of doctoral students, combined with the greater burden of parental responsibilities for women, probably plays a role here.

* Ratio of the number of doctoral students with all form of studies interrupted to the number of doctoral students studying.

Source: MEYS: Statistics of performance indicators of public and private universities, own processing.

Discontinuing doctoral studies: foreigners

Foreigners interrupt their doctoral studies to a lesser extent than Czech citizens. In full-time studies, these differences have deepened due to the slightly decreasing development of the interruption rate for foreigners and the relatively stable development for Czech citizens.

In contrast, in the combined form of study, foreigners have come closer to Czech doctoral students in terms of interruption of studies due to a steeper increase in the interruption rate.

Foreigners, especially from third countries, have less scope to interrupt full-time doctoral studies if they have obtained a residence permit in the Czech Republic for the duration of their studies based on their admission to the study.

Picture 9: Doctoral study dropout rate* for foreigners and Czech citizens by form of study

* Ratio of the number of doctoral students with all form of studies interrupted to the number of doctoral students studying

Source: MEYS: Statistics of performance indicators of public and private universities, own processing.

Openness of doctoral studies to master's graduates

Picture 10: Doctoral study capacity by fields of study

Note: The capacity is calculated as the ratio of the number of first-time enrollees in doctoral programs to the number of graduates of master's programs.

Source: MEYS: Statistics of performance indicators of public and private universities, own processing.

The openness of doctoral studies is defined as the proportion of first-time enrollees in doctoral studies to the number of doctoral graduates in the relevant year. This ratio can also be understood as the relative capacity of universities defined for doctoral studies.

The highest level of doctoral study capacity is consistently shown by natural science fields, which, despite a relatively sharp decline in 2024, remain above 50% of the capacity of master's studies. For other fields, the value of this indicator ranges from 4% (ISCED 4 and 10) to 20% (agricultural fields) in 2024.

The decline in doctoral study capacities across fields of study is influenced, among other factors, by changes in the financing of doctoral students. From 1 September 2025, the monthly income of full-time students must reach at least 1.2 times the minimum monthly wage, which represents a sharp increase compared to the previous adjustment (approx. 25 thousand CZK vs. approx. 12 thousand CZK).

Openness of doctoral studies to foreigners

The openness of doctoral programs to foreigners has been growing in the long term. The greatest dynamics are evident in agricultural fields, in which the share of graduates with foreign nationality almost tripled in 2024 compared to 2015, and in natural science fields with an almost double increase. On average, the share of foreigners increased by approximately $\frac{1}{4}$ across all fields of study. Foreigners are consistently least interested in technical fields, followed by humanities and social science fields.

Picture 11: Share of foreigners among doctoral graduates

The largest proportion of graduating foreigners are Slovak citizens, who do not have to face significant language or cultural barriers and who relatively easily find professional employment in the Czech Republic.

Citizens of the Slovak Republic across all fields made up 32% of foreign graduates. This average significantly exceeds the field of health and social care, almost twice (62%), but also the field of ICT, although not as significantly (43%).

Of the other countries, the most foreigners who graduated from doctoral studies in 2024, regardless of the field of study, were from India, Germany and the Russian Federation, who made up 8%, 7% and 5% of all graduating foreign doctoral students, respectively.

Source: MEYS: Statistics of performance indicators of public and private universities in the Czechia, own processing.

Gender structure of doctoral studies: first-time enrollees

The share of women in newly started doctoral studies increased slightly from 45% to 46% in 2015–2024. Among the subject groups with a more significant increase in women is ICT, where women, together with technical subjects, still only account for about a quarter of newly enrolled doctoral students.

In most other subject groups, women account for more than half of those enrolled in doctoral studies. The field of education and upbringing remains the most attractive for women.

Picture 12: Proportion of women among first-time enrollees in doctoral studies

Source: MEYS: Statistics of performance indicators of public and private universities in the Czechia, own processing.

Gender structure of doctoral studies: male and female graduates

As the share of women in the total number of doctoral students increases, so does their share of the total number of graduates. The dynamics of the share of women in the number of graduates is more significant than the dynamics of their share in the number of students.

In 2024, the share of women in the total number of graduates increased across all fields from 44% in 2015 to 49%.

However, this positive trend is only noticeable in a few fields, mainly in social sciences, services, technical fields and ICT. In the other six out of the ten fields monitored, the share of women decreased. The most significant decrease was in agricultural fields.

Picture 13: Proportion of women among doctoral graduates

Source: MEYS: Statistics of performance indicators of public and private universities in the Czechia, own processing.

Doctoral completion success: development over time

The development of the success rate of completing doctoral studies is monitored according to the year of commencement of studies and the status of these studies as of December 31, 2024. In principle, data on studies that were commenced by 2016 can be considered almost final, as the study should last a maximum of twice the standard duration of study, i.e. in most cases eight years.

The success rate of doctoral studies in the Czech Republic has long been low. More than 60% of doctoral studies in the Czech Republic end unsuccessfully. This situation has been worsening in recent years, as evidenced by data for the years of study initiation 2010–2017, when the share of studies completed without graduation increased from 60% to 76%. Even if a few students are still continuing their studies in 2024, their possible successful completion of their studies will not significantly affect the values.

Most doctoral studies take longer to complete than the standard study period. For example, for studies started in 2020, active studies outweigh completed studies, although the four-year standard study period has already expired in 2024.

Graf 14: Doctoral studies as of December 31, 2024 by year of study start

Source: MEYS: Statistics of performance indicators of public and private universities, own processing.

Doctoral completion success: university comparison

Picture 15: Share of students successfully completing doctoral studies at major Czech universities (as of 31 December 2024, starting year 2016)

In total, 40% of doctoral students at Czech universities will have successfully completed their studies that they started in 2015 by the end of 2024. However, only 7% did so within the expected year of graduation (PRU), another 9% within one year (PRU+1) and 24% even later.

The success rate varies significantly between individual universities. The best performers in this respect were doctoral students from the University of Chemical Technology (57%), the University of South Bohemia (46%) and the Veterinary University of Brno (46%). The high share of graduation at other universities at the Veterinary University of Brno is related to the departure of the Faculty of Pharmacy from Masaryk University in 2021.

The University of Economics (28%) and the University of West Bohemia in Pilsen (30%) are relatively far below the average success rate (41%).

Doctoral study completion success: fields of study

Among the subject groups, the highest success rates in completing doctoral studies are in natural sciences (49%), agriculture (48%) and pedagogical fields (45%).

On the other hand, ICT fields and arts and humanities are below average. In both of these fields, practice apparently does not value the achievement of a scientific degree in the expected way, so students' motivation to successfully complete doctoral studies is weakened.

Picture 16: Share of students successfully completing doctoral studies by field of study (as of 31 December 2024, starting year 2016)

Methodological note:

The data are only approximate. Given that the available success data are not sorted by ISCED, the basis was the success rate of individual faculties, which were either fully or partially assigned to individual ISCED fields.

The data only include public universities.

Source: MEYS: Statistics of performance indicators of public and private universities, own processing.

Opportunities for doctoral graduates to apply in research and development

Graduates of doctoral programs are educated to perform demanding research and development and innovation activities. Therefore, the relationship between the number of doctoral graduates and the number of jobs for researchers expressed as the number of researchers converted to full-time equivalents (FTE) is monitored.

The lowest number of doctoral graduates in relation to the number of researchers (FTE) is consistently in technical fields. In 2024, there were 22 graduates of the field per thousand researchers, which poses a problem for the development of technologically demanding production and the sophisticated technical services linked to them. These graduates, together with graduates of natural science and ICT fields, will face the fewest problems in finding employment in research and development compared to graduates of other fields.

On the contrary, graduates of social science and humanities fields will face higher competition in finding employment in such focused research and development.

Picture 17: Number of doctoral graduates per thousand researchers in individual fields

* Including education, business, administration, and law. Graduates in the Services field group are not included. All four sectors (business, government, higher education, and private non-profit) are included.

Source: MEYS: Statistics of performance indicators of public and private universities, CZSO: Research and development indicators for the Czech Republic. Own processing.

Zaměstnanost v profesích blízkých k výzkumu a vývoji

Picture 18: Professions related to research and development (R&D) – share of total

Note: The graph displays data on primary employment.

Source: Czech Statistical Office (CZSO), Labour Force Survey (LFS)

In professions most closely related to research and development (R&D) activities, the Czech Republic experienced a substantial increase in employment between 2014 and 2024. By far the largest contributor to this trend was the growth in the number of software developer positions. Moderate increases were also recorded among specialists in the social sciences and humanities, mathematicians, biologists, and specialists in engineering and natural sciences.

The share of individuals whose primary employment is in positions as university teachers or R&D managers has remained stable over the monitored period.

Profesní uplatnění absolventů doktorského studia

Approximately half of doctoral graduates work in occupations that involve research and development activities or are closely related to R&D. The share of PhD graduates employed in these occupations remained stable over the period 2014–2024, alongside a simultaneous increase in the number of individuals with doctoral education. Owing to the growth in employment in R&D and R&D-related occupations, the prospects for adequate employment of doctoral graduates have therefore not deteriorated.

Only a very small proportion of PhD graduates are employed in software developer occupations. Thus, the dynamically expanding field of software development has so far not generated many positions in which the competencies of doctoral graduates are utilised.

Picture 19: Primary Employment of PhD Holders in the Czech Republic

Source: Czech Statistical Office (CZSO), Labour Force Survey (LFS)

